

during land preparation at the IARI farm during the 1992 kharif (wet) season. Fresh leucaena (2.3% N on an oven-dry basis) was chopped into 2-3 cm lengths and incorporated at 30 t/ha (about 90 kg N) 3 d before transplanting. Soil-based inocula of BGA (*Aulosira*, *Tolypothrix*, *Scytonema*, *Nostoc*, *Anabaena*, and *Plectonema*) at 30 kg/ha were broadcast at 8 d after transplanting (DT) on standing water. Prilled urea was applied in three splits at transplanting, 35 DT, and at flowering.

Pooled data showed that rice hull did not significantly increase the grain yield of Pusa Basmati 1, although a constant increase in grain yield was obtained by adding rice hull regardless of different BGA, leucaena, and

prilled urea treatments (see table). BGA and urea at both 30 and 60 kg N/ha had synergistic effects in fields that received rice hull. In untreated fields, a synergistic effect was observed only for urea at 60 kg N and in BGA treatments.

The significant yield increase achieved with BGA and urea combinations when compared with similar levels of urea alone suggests that a starter dose of fertilizer N is important for establishing BGA in mild alkaline soil. Results revealed that BGA contributed about 30 kg N/ha when applied with urea to plots where rice hull was added. No such synergistic effect was noticed with the leucaena and BGA combination. However, cuttings of leucaena

increased rice yield by more than 1 t/ha, with or without rice hull.

In northern India, sandy loam soils with low organic matter content are generally poor, both physically and in N status. Rice has been grown increasingly in this region during the past three decades, with burning of hulls near rice mills a common practice. Instead, hulls could be applied on the fields to improve the overall soil physical property and organic matter status. We suggest that farmers should apply rice hulls, combined with leucaena and BGA, to substantially cut down on costly fertilizer N use while improving the soil. ■

Fertilizer management-organic sources

Influence of intercropping green manure in wet seeded rice

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The effects of incorporating intercropped green manure (GM) in wet seeded rice cultivated during 1992-94 were studied at ACRI.

The soil was a sandy clay loam classified as Typic Ultisol. The initial nutrient status was 233 kg N/ha, 17.1 kg P/ha, and 246 kg K/ha in 1992-93 and 226 kg N/ha, 16.2 kg

P/ha, and 244 kg K/ha in 1993-94. *Sesbania rostrata* usually has delayed germination when sown under puddled conditions. so instead, it was raised separately and 20-d-old seedlings were planted. Seeds of *S. speciosa* were dibbled at 3 kg/ha.

Five days after IR20 was sown, both GMs were intercropped in the main field in the empty space of 30 cm and maintained at a 1.5-m interval. Intra-row spacings of 15 and 30 cm and incorporation at 30 and 45 d after planting (DAP)/sowing for the GMs were compared with a no-GM control in a randomized block design with three replications. Fresh green biomass was assessed at incorporation.

More green biomass was obtained when *S. rostrata* seedlings were planted at 15 cm spacing and incorporated 45 DAP than with the other treatments. When compared with the no-GM control, the yield increase with this method was 38.4% more in 1992-93 and 44.5% more in 1993-94. Because of its initial slow growth rate, *S. speciosa* biomass was lower than that of *S. rostrata*. Incorporating green biomass in the standing ricefield positively increased the yield parameters of panicle number, panicle length, and filled grains per panicle, resulting in higher rice yield (see table).

Wet seeded rice benefits from intercropping 20-d-old *S. rostrata* seedlings at intra-row spacing of 15 cm and incorporation at 45 DAP. ■

Effect of intra-row spacing and time of incorporation of green manure on biomass production, yield parameters, and yield of wet seeded rice. ACRI. Madurai, India. 1992-94.

Green manure	Treatments		1992-93						1993-94					
	Intra-row spacing (cm)	Time of incorporation (DAP) ^a	Fresh green biomass (t/ha)	N input (kg/ha)	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grams/panicle (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Fresh green biomass (t/ha)	N input (kg/ha)	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Sesbania rostrata</i>	15	30	1.30	42.9	8.0	18.2	90.0	3.96	1.23	38.7	7.4	17.3	87.1	3.59
	15	45	1.64	53.5	8.0	18.3	91.1	4.04	1.50	49.2	7.6	17.3	88.2	3.80
	30	30	1.05	34.8	7.8	18.2	88.0	3.61	0.88	29.4	7.0	17.0	87.1	3.51
	30	45	0.76	25.4	7.4	18.0	85.1	3.51	0.73	24.5	6.8	17.1	86.2	3.51
<i>Sesbania speciosa</i>	15	30	0.14	3.6	7.2	17.7	83.3	3.31	0.13	3.4	6.4	16.8	85.2	3.22
	15	45	0.18	4.5	7.2	17.6	83.2	3.22	0.18	4.5	6.4	16.8	85.1	3.10
	30	30	0.07	1.9	7.2	17.4	83.1	3.04	0.06	1.6	6.2	16.2	83.1	2.92
	30	45	0.09	2.5	7.0	17.4	83.1	2.98	0.08	2.3	6.0	16.2	82.5	2.87
No green manure	-	-	-	-	7.0	17.0	80.1	2.92	-	-	4.8	16.0	78.3	2.63
CD (P = 0.05)	-	-	-	-	ns	0.2	0.9	0.17	-	-	0.8	0.7	0.2	0.40

^aDAP = days after planting.